

**A CONVENIENT METHOD FOR DEVELOPING
LISTENING SKILLS IN LANGUAGE LEARNING (LISTENING)
(ENGLISH AS AN EXAMPLE)**

Yuldasheva Nasiba Murodilla's daughter

"International school of finance technology and science"

English language science teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698555>

Annotation . This in the article English in the language listening to understand skill formation ways about information given _ In particular , listening to understand in development main language phonemic , phonetic and intonation components deep interpretation done _

Key words : language components , linguistic and extralinguistic difficulties , language skills .

It is known each how the language learning speech 4 main activities practice by means of done is increased . These are speak , read , write and listening to understand processes is , in particular , foreign their languages in learning speech of activity this types to teach important is because _ they are through information is given and is taken . Information get listening to understand and reading through done if it increases , information to give to speak and to write through done increases .

Speech of activity shape two ie oral and written speech _ Oral speech to teach listening and to speak to teach , write speech while reading and to write to teach own into takes _

" Listening to understand speech of activity one type being , it is receptive speech to the activity enters _

Listening to understand of the speaker speech from radio , tape recorder , compact from disk and communication during listening understanding , information is to get He is some in the literature It is also called auditory . It is complicated speech because it is an activity listener quickly form acceptance do it to get , in memory save stay necessary , etc without him again see , read , understand take for source , condition , means no _ Inspections that's it shows that students and in students listening to understand to speak than less progressive reached _ A student when reading and seeing listening to understand than six times a lot information you can The reason him on less It's because it works , it's because it's complicated . Listening to understand to speak indispensable is part of Listening to understand and to speak oral speech organize will do "

Speech listening ability the following of components consists of :

- A) phonemic listening ability ,
- B) phonetic listening ability ,
- C) intonation listening ability _

Phonemic listening ability of phonemes phonological ie meaning separator features differentiate for service does _ Phonetic listening ability while speech of sounds phonetic feature differentiate for service does , that is meaning non-distinguishing speech sounds right listen get ability means _ Intonational listening ability sentence and in sentences tone right advanced get for service does _ This ability The type is also the above such as important importance occupation is enough Methodist scientist T. Sattarov higher education in institutions listening to understand to teach linguistic and psychological studying the

characteristics came out and listening to understand difficulties the following to factors linked by :

1. The individual age of the listener features ;
2. Perception to do speed _
3. Conditions ;
4. Speed ;
5. Information amount , volume ;
6. Perception to do supports ;
7. Exhaustion

Yakubov I. listening to understand important speech activity type as price gave and listening to understand 3 types in teaching difficulties emphasizing past :

1. Extralinguistic
2. Linguistic
3. Psychological

Extralinguistic difficulties the following : - being listened to of speech mechanics , that is mechanic device using put broadcast ; - of speech Timbre and speed are being heard condition , situation ; - the student's attention _ - of speech how many times listening ; - listening to understand in the process support tools , meaningful of pictures to be and another that's it such as factors .

Linguistic difficulties to the language about difficulties being Rogova G. such 3 types of challenges explaining gives : - phonetic difficulties ie to each other near sounds listening to understand and in differentiation meeting difficulties ; - lexicon difficulties ie to each other pronunciation near the words listening to understand with depends difficulties ; - grammar difficult people , that is grammar the rules with depends has been difficulties (English language analytical language from being come comes out)

Psychological difficulties individual characteristics of the learner with depends .

Psychological point of view from the point of view speech listening in understanding of learners memory important role plays _ Speech when listened to , in it information in memory save if he stays , him again to listen a must it's not and assignments execution is the same so much it becomes easier .

Methodist Jalolov J. listening to understand difficulties as follows classifies : - language difficulties (meaning each different pronunciation _ own words) ; - to the content about difficulties ; - speech perception to do conditions with depends difficulties ; - linguistics point of view in terms of happen to be difficulties - audiotext to the structure about difficulties . This difficulties prevention get for listening to understand for right audio text selection must will be Ours in our opinion , audio text in choosing the following requirements action to do need : - text ideological and educational expensive have to be - of students to their age own mother in the language and foreign in the language speech to the experience suitable fall _ - in the student interest wake up issue lighting ; - logically right construction ; - of speech different forms cover get _ - extra information of the elements a lot not to be

High study in their countries English language of teaching practical from the goals one oral speech is to teach . This is it study of their countries software requirements according to , students English in the language oral information to give , to talk get and studied to the topic depends English in the language speech listening understand get qualifications acquisitions Demand will be done .

Today's in the day foreign language to learn has been Demand is increasing . Foreign languages learners the following in skills ie speaking , writing , listening to understand and reading such as by developing goes _ Like this language skills during shaping and boorish student one how much to difficulties face will come An example as listening to understand skill will receive if so , the language in learners in pronunciation , correct in writing or in understanding , vocabulary wealth lack of kbi problems their foreign language to learn has been passion lost to go reason is happening in learners attention one to the place total not getting , not being thorough , listening to understand skill lower stage stay to leave means _ Listening the material judging the speaker as uninteresting criticism to do , only the facts listen , pay attention laziness these are including _

Listening to understand skill one how much problems solve for movies view , group in presentations participation is open kind of to questions answer giving , listening to understand exercises perform with one at the time that's it event in our minds formation , listening skill development consequential methods . That's it on purpose English language learners in the example listening to understand skill which develops efficient method recommendation we will

Language learners for special prepared audio (2 minutes English) one times will be heard : " Your memory improve " (Improving your memory). Second times while we listen verbatim dictation in the form of is written : I think you might find it quite useful 246

... Of course text inside student didn't know the words to be told natural _ That's it due to , text transcription student himself what he wrote with one by one check the mistakes correct goes to :

kinaesthetic = kinaesthetic . Checked text student by again one there is is heard wanderer with together is read . Text inside new the words to the bottom drawing them in the text where way to be used attention to give it is necessary From this after new words memorize for dictionary to the notebook written : intuitive sense= doing something based on feeling rather than facts or proof. new words fast and easy remember to stay for them participating sentences will be compiled , this while oral in speech application and in pronunciation in improvement efficient help gives : Encoding information is more effective way. Summary by doing so to speak language while studying listening to understand skill in raising special audios listening him above six from the stage otkasza , of course , is effective the result gives

References:

- 1.Jalolov J. Foreign language teaching methodology . " Teacher . 2011.
- 2.Z. No'monova , G. Orinboyeva . DEVELOPING LISTENING SKILLS IN LANGUAGE LEARNING (LISTENING)
linguistzebo@gmail.comhttps://elar.rsvpu.ru/bitstream/123456789/39154/1/avsorpo_2020_3_070.pdf